

Application of Statistical Arbitrages through pairs trading

Dr. Amol Gawande¹, Sarika Pansare² and Adil Ejaj³

¹Associate Professor, Global Business School and Research Centre, Pune, Maharashtra, India

² Assistant Professor and ³Student, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India

Abstract:

Arbitrages are commonly observed in trading. For instance, Infosys may trade at Rs.1000 at the BSE and at the same time exchange hands at Rs.1050 at the NSE. In this situation, a street-smart trader will buy at the BSE and sell at the NSE and profit. Traders have been fascinated by this phenomenon and look at the arbitrages as a profit-making opportunity. They have worked out different strategies to play within such conditions. One of the popular strategies is pairs trading. This paper carries a conceptual discussion of the different terms and explains how the strategies are actually implemented.

Keywords: Statistical arbitrage, Pairs trading, Stock Markets

Introduction

In most basic terms, arbitrage refers to a trade opportunity that entails exploiting an inefficiency in the securities market by simultaneously buying and selling a security for a profit (Ehrman, 2006). It is an opportunity of making a profit in the securities market without risk and net investment of capital (Delbean and Schachermayer, 2006). Statistical arbitrage represents statistically significant deviations from historically identified average price relationships. It is taking counteracting positions in securities that are historically or mathematically associated, but taking these positions at times when their inter-relationship has been temporarily skewed.

The practice of statistical arbitrage began in 1978 on the trading desk of Morgan Stanley, with a trade comprising of going long on General Motors (NYSE: GM) and short on Ford (NYSE: F). It is accredited to Wall Street quantitative analyst Nunzio Tartaglia, who, with a mathematics team, computer scientists, and physicists, wanted to establish quantitative arbitrage strategies using state-of-the-art statistical tools. This rapidly extended to general pairs trading and then, in the 1990s, further broadened to comprise long and short market-neutral portfolios composed of groups of securities selected from stocks, ETFs, options, index futures, and index options. It can also include commodities, fixed income, and other derivatives. Some examples of securities for statistical arbitrage strategies include cross-listed stocks, futures, stock indexes, pairs of stocks, foreign currency, portfolio of stocks, and foreign currencies (Zacks, 2011).

One of the most frequently referred to statistical arbitrage tools is the 'pairs trading' strategy. (Ehrman, 2006) defined pairs trading as "a nondirectional, relative-value investment strategy that seeks to identify two companies with similar characteristics whose equity securities are currently trading at a price relationship that is outside their historical trading range. This investment strategy entails buying the undervalued security while short-selling the overvalued security, thereby maintaining market neutrality". Thus, it is fundamentally a market-neutral strategy that obtains its returns from the inter-relation between its long position and short position. The relative performance governs the strategy's performance and not by the absolute performance of the securities involved.

Pairs trading presupposes that while markets might not be in equilibrium, they steer towards a rational equilibrium, and the trader has an opportunity to take utmost benefit of the discrepancies from the equilibrium (Göncü and Akyildirim, 2016). The theoretical explanation for the correlated or similar security prices movement arises from Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT). According to this theory, if two securities have absolutely the same risk factor exposures, then the two securities' expected return for a stated time interval is the same.

Although hedge funds and investment banks commonly use the pairs trading technique of statistical arbitrage, empirical studies testing this strategy's profitability are scarce, especially in the Indian context. The most significant and extensive study testing the pairs trading strategy and its profitability is that of Gatev *et al.* (2006), which focused on the U.S. market. Their study matched stocks into pairs with a minimum distance between normalized historical prices. The trading done through this strategy for 1962-2002 yielded annualized risk-adjusted returns of about 11 percent.

Many academic researches provide frameworks to carry out pairs trading. Vidyamurthy (2004) presented an implementation strategy based on cointegration by explaining the nexus between pricing theory and pairs trading theory. Many studies claimed that usage of statistical arbitrage strategies based on cointegration with optimal weight allocations would generate significant abnormal annual returns between 2.44 percent and 11.96 percent (Norden & Schaller, 1993 and Grobys, 2012). In a comprehensive review of statistical arbitrage and cointegration, Pole (2007) stated that the portfolio was anticipated to generate a positive return as valuations converge. The mean-reversion paradigm is specifically related to securities being transiently over or under priced compared to one or more reference securities and market over-reaction to it (Lo and MacKinlay, 1990).

Elliott *et al.* (2005), using a 'mean-reverting Gaussian Markov chain model,' provided a detailed framework for pairs trading. Huck (2009) applied multicriteria decision techniques for choosing pairs for pairs trading. The most prominent work, Gatev *et al.* (2006), evaluated a large sample of US stocks over 1962 and 2002. Although these studies used different methods to assess the pairs trading strategy's performance and hence are not directly comparable, pairs trading displayed a positive performance in all of them.

Bossaerts and Green (1989) and Jagannathan and Viswanathan (1988) found that the pairs trading strategy might be supported within an equilibrium asset-pricing framework with common nonstationary factors. They opined that if the long and short components fluctuated with common nonstationary factors, then the component portfolios' prices would be cointegrated, and the pairs trading strategy would be expected to work. Statistical Arbitrage denies the securities market to be in any economic equilibrium, which is crucial for an efficient market (Jarrow, 1988).

The existence of arbitrage opportunities contradicts the efficient market hypothesis given by (Fama, 1970). The hypothesis states that securities are justly priced in the market and that arbitrage situations cannot prevail. Hence, it seems to be a paradox, ipso facto, that the market exhibits efficiency on the one hand and yet have arbitrage opportunities. The plausible explanation is that investors and traders who seek arbitrage opportunities are themselves the reason for the existence of efficient markets. By pursuing and exploiting market inefficiencies, they essentially exclude these inefficiencies in the mechanism by enabling prices to reach their appropriate level. Although the market is broadly efficient, there is generally a time lag in this efficiency, which explains arbitrage opportunities. Therefore, it is not necessary to resolve the paradox.

India is a strong emerging economy. Huge investment and trading activities from all over the world are directed to the Indian securities market. Global hedge funds are now prioritizing the Indian securities market for their emerging market investments. Many strategies and algorithms are now implemented and tested in the Indian securities market, and statistical arbitrage has been a profitable quantitative strategy. There are many platforms available in India where one can trade using statistical arbitrage techniques. These platforms do not provide any documented evidence of profitability.

Statistical Arbitrage, or Stat Arb for short, has a history of being a highly profitable algorithmic trading strategy for many big hedge funds and investment banks. Statistical arbitrage initiated around the 1980s, led by Morgan Stanley and other banks, witnessed wide acceptance in financial markets. The popularity of the strategy continued in the markets for more than twenty years, and different models were created around it to make huge profits. To put it in simple terms, Statistical arbitrage consists of a set of quantitatively driven algorithmic trading strategies. These strategies try to exploit the relative price movements across thousands of financial instruments by analyzing the price differences and price patterns between them. The end outcome of such strategies is to generate alpha (higher than normal profits) for the trading firms. A point to be noted here is that Statistical arbitrage is not a high-frequency trading (HFT) strategy. Rather it can be classified as a medium-frequency strategy where the trading period ranges from a course of a few hours to a few days.

Concepts used by Statistical Arbitrage Strategies

To analyze the price differences and price patterns, the strategists make use of statistical and mathematical models. Statistical arbitrage strategies can also be designed using factors such as corporate activity, lead/lag effects, short-term momentum, etc., apart from using the price data alone. This type of approach is called as a multi-factor Statistical Arbitrage model. The various concepts used in statistical arbitrage strategies include:

- AutoRegression and Cointegration
- Volatility modeling
- Pattern finding techniques
- Time Series Analysis
- Efficient frontier analysis
- Principal Components Analysis
- Machine learning techniques etc.

Types of Statistical Arbitrage Strategies

The various Statistical arbitrage strategies include:

- Cross Asset Arbitrage
- Market Neutral Arbitrage
- ETF Arbitrage
- Cross Market Arbitrage

Cross Asset Arbitrage

This model is based on the price discrepancy between a financial asset and its underlying. For instance, between a stock index future and the stocks that form the index.

Market Neutral Arbitrage

It involves assuming a long position in an undervalued asset and shorting an overvalued asset at the same time. The asset is believed to have similar volatilities, and thus, a rise in the market will lead the long position to appreciate in value, and the short position will lead to depreciation by approximately the same amount. The positions get squared off when the assets fall back to their normalized value.

ETF arbitrage

Exchange-Traded Fund arbitrage can be explained as a form of cross-asset arbitrage that identifies discrepancies between an Exchange Traded Fund's value and its underlying assets.

Cross Market Arbitrage

Cross Market Arbitrage seeks to exploit the price discrepancy of the same asset across markets. The strategy one buys an asset in the lower-valuing market and sells it in the more highly valuing market.

Pairs Trading

Statistical Arbitrage is an evolved version of pair trading strategies, in which stocks are put into pairs by market-based or fundamental similarities. When one stock in a pair outperforms the other, the lesser performing stock is purchased along with the expectation that it will climb its outperforming partner. At the same time, the position is insulated/hedged from market changes/movements by short selling the other outperforming stock. Due to the large number of stocks included in the statistical arbitrage strategy, the high portfolio turnover, and the relatively small size of the spread one is trying to capture, the strategy is often implemented in an automated fashion, and significant attention is paid to reducing transaction or trading costs. Statistical arbitrage strategy has become a popular player at both hedge funds and investment banks. There is often some *correlation*—the extent to which prices move in the same direction—between any two different assets. Mostly, the prices for two assets in the same sector have a high correlation. For instance, if there is new car regulation, then it is quite likely that the stock prices for both Ford and Telsa decline—implying that they are highly correlated. We can see similar behavior when regulatory news for crypto is announced—prices of many crypto assets increase or decrease at the same time. Arbitrage opportunities exist when correlations diverge from the general norm. Suppose two virtual currencies usually move in lockstep, but after some news announcement, the price of currency P decreases by 20%, but the price of currency Q decreases by only 5%. One could buy the underperforming coin (currency P) and sell the over-performing coin (currency Q), under the assumption that at equilibrium, both the price of both coins will settle around a decrease of 10% on the day. Such a trading methodology is called *pairs trading*. In pairs trading, it is assumed that the two assets will fall back to their equilibrium correlation levels instead of the price level (as in the mean reversion model). However, by assuming two opposing positions—selling one asset and buying the other—we need not worry about moving in the same direction, increasing or decreasing in price. Rather, we only care about the relationship between them, which (often but not necessarily always) is statistically more significant than any individual price level prediction. Moreover, since two positions have been taken instead of one, if the pair's prices do converge as per their historical pattern, we might get double the profit, unlike the mean reversion case.

The risk in this model can be understood from the possibility of the pair diverging instead of converging once we have taken our positions, which can cause us to lose on both legs of our trade. This model also requires multiple initial parameters: we must choose our assets of interest, determine their current correlation, set an entry-level when we correlate 'break,' and manage a take profit and stop loss level for both of the positions we took. Convergence and divergence are often determined by confidence intervals, which can be created using tools like standard deviations, Bollinger bands, and range trading, among others.

How Statistical Arbitrage Strategy Works?

Securities such as stocks quite often tend to trade in upward and downward cycles. A quantitative method tries to capitalize on these trends. The trending behavior of quantitative trading uses software packages to

track trends or patterns. Trends discovered are based on the frequency, volume, and the price of a security at which it is traded.

Figure 1: Statistical arbitrage example

Source: www.quantinsti.com/blog/statistical-arbitrage

In the figure above, Ambuja and ACC's stock prices are represented over six years. It can be seen that both the stocks stayed quite close to each other during the entire period of six years, barring only a few instances of separation. In these separation periods, an arbitrage opportunity arises based on the belief that the stock prices will move closer again.

The key in identifying such opportunities lies in two important factors:

- Recognizing or identifying the pairs which require advanced statistical tests and time series analysis and
- Fixing the entry-exit points for the strategy to leverage the market position

There are lots of in-built pair trading indicators on popular platforms to identify and trade in pairs. However, many times, transaction costs, which are the crucial factor in earning profits from a strategy, are generally not considered in calculating the projected returns. Therefore, it is recommended that traders make their statistical arbitrage strategies giving due consideration to all the factors at the time of backtesting that will affect the trade's final profitability.

Risks in Statistical Arbitrage

Even though Statistical arbitrage strategies have mopped up lots of profits for Quantitative trading firms, these strategies come along with their own set of risks. Following are some of the risks faced:

- The strategy heavily relies on the mean reversion of prices to their historical or predicted normal. This may not necessarily happen in some cases, and the prices can continue to drift away from the historical normal.
- Financial markets are in continuous flux and evolve based on events occurring across the world. Hence, there is no guarantee of profit from statistical arbitrage all the time. In other words, losses may also be incurred in certain situations.

"Pairs trading is when a simultaneous long position is taken in one stock while a short position is taken in another.

The stocks must be highly correlated, meaning they move in the same direction most of the time. Typically, this is seen in the stocks of companies that are very similar, such as Coca-Cola Bottling Co. (KO) and Pepsico Inc. (PEP), or Ford (F) and General Motors (GM).

Since these companies' stocks move similarly due to their similar business—we always must check to make sure they are moving similarly—when their stocks diverge, it presents a trading opportunity. The strategy is to buy the stock that is underperforming and short-sell the one that is outperforming the other. Doing this safely requires some research and risk controls.

Pairs Trading Considerations

Before utilizing this strategy, we first must see if two stocks are correlated. We want them to move in tandem most of the time; that way, when they diverge from one another, if history holds, then eventually they will revert back to trading in tandem and a profit can be made.

Figure 2: F (red) and GM (green) Comparison Daily Chart (Percentage Scale)

Source: Freestockcharts.com

Figure 2 shows that over this time frame, Ford and General Motors often move in tandem. When they separated, it presented an opportunity to short-sell GM when outperforming and buy Ford when underperforming. As long as the stocks eventually come back to trading in tandem, then a profit is made. In this case, they did.

The overall market direction does not matter. As long as the stocks separate and then come back together, a profit is made, even if both stocks drop or both rally but get back in sync by doing it.

That is the theory, but deciding when to take a pairs trade, how to control risk, and when to take profit is a more precise matter.

Stockcharts.com allows you to plot a chart that shows the ratio of one stock compared to another. Figure 3 shows the share price of Ford divided by the share price of General Motors. The ratio is currently 0.51, meaning Ford is almost exactly half the price of GM.

Figure 3. F / GM Share Price with 200-day Moving Average and 200 Day Bollinger Bands (2.5 Standard Deviations)

Source: StockCharts.com

Two hundred days moving average is applied to get a "normal" ratio (currently 0.45). Bollinger Bands are also applied (200 periods and 2.5 standard deviations) to spot times when the ratio has moved significantly away from the norm, offering a trading opportunity.

The next section shows how to pick an entry and get out, but position sizing must be addressed before that. According to current data, the stocks are priced differently; General Motors is about twice as much as Ford. This means we cannot buy the same number of shares in each. We must calibrate each position.

The easiest way to determine position size is to set a fixed dollar amount for each trade side, say \$10,000. Buy \$10,000 worth of one stock and sell \$10,000 worth of the other stock. The exposure is the same, but the number of shares held in each will be different.

Pairs Trading Example Explained

Consider the trade that occurred in December 2013. Ford declined steeply in value relative to GM, as is shown in both figures 2 and 3.

On December 6, the ratio breaks below 2.5 standard deviations (lower red Bollinger Bands) from the 200-day norm. Ford is falling, and GM is rallying; the stocks are diverging. While trade can be taken at the exact moment, the ratio penetrates the 2.5 standard deviations Bollinger Band, and it is prudent to wait for both the stock prices and the ratio to start converging (moving back toward normal) again before taking the trade. In this case, we do not see the ratio begin to trend back higher until January 2. By waiting for the ratio to begin heading back toward the norm, we avoid holding a losing position for longer than we need to (in this case, it would have been almost a month), and we can also place a stop below the recent low in our long trade and above the recent high in our short trade.

Therefore, enter trades when the ratio has gone beyond 2.5 standard deviations from the 200-day norm and is starting to move back toward the norm. Exit when the ratio comes within 0.02 points of the 200-day norm.

This is how the trade looks on the ratio chart.

Figure 4 F / GM Ratio Pairs Trade Entry and Exit

Source: StockCharts.com

Buy Ford near the close on January 2 at \$15.44. Place a stop loss below the recent low at \$15.10.

Short-sell GM near the close on January 2 at \$40.95. Place a stop above the recent high at \$41.85.

Figure 5 Pairs Trade with Entries, Stops, and Exit

Source: FreeStockCharts.com

If each side of the trade is allocated \$10,000, we buy 647 shares of Ford (\$10,000 / \$15.44) and sell 244 shares of General Motors (\$10,000 / \$40.95).

Closeout trade near the market close on January 24 because the ratio has moved to within 0.02 of the norm (200-day average). Therefore, we can conclude the price relationship has reestablished itself, and our reason for entering the trade has now diminished.

GM is closed at \$36.83 and Ford at \$15.83.

Profit collected is:

General Motors: $\$40.95 - \$36.83 = \$4.12 \times 244 \text{ shares} = \$1,005.28$

Ford: $\$15.83 - \$15.44 = 0.39 \times 647 = \252.33

Net Profit: $\$1,005.28 + \$252.33 = \$1,257.61$

The short trade creates a cash inflow that offsets the long position's outflow, so there is minimal cash outlay. If calculating the return based on the initial \$20,000 in positions, the return is greater than 6% in less than a month.

Not all pairs trades will work out this well; sometimes, only one trade will be profitable and the other a loser; other times, both trades may be unprofitable.

The stop losses also contained risk to a small amount of capital, and the profit potential was much greater than the risk with these stops in place.

If either position gets stopped out, exit the other trade as well. With this style of pairs trading, you always have two positions or no positions.

Pros and Cons of Pairs Trading

Pros include the strategy being market neutral. Just address the dynamic that is going on between the stocks and little regard or time needs to be committed to studying broader market conditions. The strategy is also quite flexible; shorter-term traders can use less of a standard deviation or a shorter time frame (i.e., 30-minute chart) to trigger more trade signals.

Cons include the possibility that divergence can last much longer than expected, or the prices can simply continue to diverge based on fundamental changes in company structure or performance. This is why a risk limit must be set to avoid catastrophe situations where the two stocks continue to move more and more out of sync. The strategy also goes against traditional trend trading concepts of buying the strongest stocks and selling the weakest – pairs trading does the opposite.

This strategy is also subjective. The price must diverge, and then we wait to take the trades until the prices start to converge again. While this is theoretically a safer approach, it takes skill and practice to develop that timing.

Traders must also consider a stock's beta. Two similar stocks that have very different betas indicate a discrepancy in volatility. If one stock is much more volatile than the other, it could cause issues with the trade. Ideally, pairs trade with stocks that are correlated and have similar betas.

Conclusion

Pairs trading involves taking a long and short trade simultaneously in two typically highly correlated stocks with similar volatility. A long position is taken when one stock underperforms by a certain threshold, and a short trade is taken in the outperformer, with the intent that the stocks will eventually revert to the historical norm, thus resulting in a profit. If the stocks do revert to being highly correlated, the trade is profitable, but risk controls in the form of stops should be used to avoid situations where stocks continue to diverge. Reversions to the norm can take a long time, so traders must weigh which trades are worth the potential wait and risk and which are not.

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